

**Protection of Traditional Knowledge in India, Its Trajectory and Place in the Intellectual
Property Rights Regime: An Analysis**

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Abstract

Protection of Traditional knowledge (herein after TK) of the indigenous communities has been one of the most complicated issues of the Intellectual Property Rights Regime. The protection of TK has been pushed to back seat with the development of individual private property rights regime, thus keeping TK outside the purview of the intellectual property protection mechanism. The need to protect TK has caught attention of the international fraternity only recently but the national governments were imposed with the duty to set standard for the protection of TK long ago. India is a store house of abundant TK. It has been estimated that about 12 % of 6000 species of potential medicinal plants is under threat due to factors like loss of habitat, environmental degradation and undurable ways of cultivation and harvesting. Documentation of TK, innovative patent system and a sui generis system can go a long way in protection of TK, combat bio-piracy and benefit sharing from exploitation of such TK with the local communities